

THERMOAGEING OF COLLOIDS. PART II. VARIATION OF THE VISCOSITY AND OPACITY.

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In a previous communication (Joshi and P. V. J. Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 217) results were recorded for change in μ_D , the refractive index produced by *thermoageing* some 19 colloids at different concentrations. In view of the fact that changes in viscosity and opacity have been widely employed to measure the corresponding degree of coagulation produced (for evidence to the contrary, *cf.* Joshi and co-workers, *vide infra*) and the possible analogy between 'ageing' and coagulation it was considered desirable to examine the influence of 'thermoageing' on the above properties. It may also be mentioned that while the previous work on 'thermoageing' has been designed chiefly to study it in relation to coagulation (Davies, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 274), detailed data are not available in the literature for changes in the more important physical properties consequent on 'thermoageing', with the exception perhaps of an earlier paper from these laboratories (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The colloid solutions of As_2S_3 , MnO_2 , Sb_2S_3 , Fe_2O_3 and Prussian blue were prepared and their colloid contents estimated as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*); that of HgS was prepared by adding, in small quantities and with repeated shaking, from H_2S water to $N/10-Hg(CN)_2$ solution, until just a trace of the gas was perceptible. It was found that the colloid showed sensible coagulation on standing for about 10 days. The *thermoageing* experiments were, therefore, carried out with a fresh sol. The molybdenum blue was prepared by reducing with H_2S an acidified (with H_2SO_4) solution of ammonium molybdate, while boiling hot. The excess of H_2S was next removed by a current of hydrogen and the sol rendered electrolyte-free by dialysis. Selenium sol was prepared by reducing with a stream of SO_2 with continuous shaking, a solution of about 1 g. of SeO_2 in 500 c.c. of water after addition of about 20 c.c. of gelatine. Before reduction the solution was warmed to 50° . The stability of the colloid was such that just slight sedimentation ensued after about a month. Colloidal vanadous acid was prepared by dispersing a small amount of V_2O_3 by repeatedly taking it up with water. About 10% aluminium acetate was added drop by drop to boiling water with continuous

shaking till the faint smell of acetic acid was just perceptible. This was next boiled for about 15 minutes, when the smell of the acid disappeared. The Al_2O_3 sol, thus obtained, was quite clear and stable. Suspensions of the linseed and *til* oil were prepared by the precipitation method described by Joshi (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, **34**, 197; *cf.* also, *J. Bombay Univ.*, 1935, **4**, 140).

A definite volume measured at a fixed temperature of each of the above sols was 'thermoaged' by refluxing it on a water-bath for 24 hours (except in the case of colloidal HgS, selenium and Al_2O_3 for which the times were shorter). A very slight reduction of volumes occurred in some cases, which was made up by adding the appropriate quantity of twice distilled water.

The viscosity (relative to that of water at the same temperature taken as unity) of a sample before and after 'thermoageing' was measured by Scarpa's method with the modifications described previously (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 330). These measurements were repeated at least twice with two independent specimens of the original sol in each case, and in some, with two dilutions of the colloid.

The change in transparency for white light by *thermoageing* was determined by means of a Duboscq colorimeter as described in a previous paper (Joshi and Kulkarni, *ibid.*, 1936, **13**, 441). Data in the 4th and 5th columns in Table I show respectively the heights in mm. of each of the sols before and after *thermoageing* matched for equal transparency.

TABLE I.

Influence of thermoageing on the viscosity and transparency.

Colloid content. (g./litre).	V i s c o s i t y		T r a n s p a r e n c y		Remarks.
	Before.	After.	Before.	After.	
As_2S_3 (3.05 g.)	1.012	1.006	56 mm.	50 mm.	
" "	1.013	1.004	33	29	
MnO_2 (1.46 g.)	1.002	1.008	20	25.3	
" "	1.003	1.009	15	19	
HgS (6.18 g.)	1.010	1.007 (5 mins.)	0.5	0.75	Coagulated in 1 hr, at about 97° ; thermo-aged for short periods as shown. Colour changes from dark brown to dark grey.
" "	1.008	1.007 (0.5 hr.)	"	"	
Sb_2S_3 (1.6 g.)	1.003	1.002	35	38.1	

Table I (contd.).

Colloid content (g./litre).	Viscosity		Transparency		Remarks.
	Before.	After.	Before.	After.	
Sb ₂ S ₃ (1.6 g.)	1.004	1.002	35	38.1	
" (0.80 g.)	1.003	1.001	65	67.5	
" "	1.003	1.001	65	67.5	
Fe ₂ O ₃ (2.0 g.)	1.023	1.016	30	27.5	
" "	1.023	1.015	40	36.0	
" "	1.023	1.015	45	40.0	
" (1.0 g.)	1.014	1.010	35	30.0	
" "	1.014	1.010	50	43.5	
" "	1.014	1.009	60	52.2	
Fe ₄ [Fe(CN) ₆] ₃ (0.5 g.)	1.008	1.007	—	—	Colour changes from blue to green.
" "	1.008	1.007	—	—	
MoO ₃ (2.5 g.)	1.009	1.010	37	40	Colour changes sensibly from blue to violet blue.
" "	1.008	1.009	46	50	
" (1.25 g.)	1.006	1.007	50	55	
" "	1.006	1.007	50	55	
Se (1.2 g.)	1.004	1.004	50	18	Viscosity and transparency mea- surements were made 3 hrs. after 'thermoaging.' Longer treatment produced floccula- tion.
" "	1.004	1.004	60	20	
V ₂ O ₅ (3.2 g.)	1.020	1.042	9	6	The transparency of the normal sol is poor.
" "	1.023	1.042	—	—	
" (1.06 g.)	1.006	1.007	19	14	" "
" "	1.006	1.008	—	—	
Al ₂ O ₃ (0.5 g.)	1.011	1.02	—	—	The sol was 'thermoaged' for about 10 hrs.
" "	1.010	1.019	—	—	
Linseed oil emulsion	1.024	1.016			Creaming is pro- duced to a small extent on 'thermoaging.'
" "	1.023	1.016			
Til oil emulsion	1.025	1.072			
" "	1.025	1.072			

DISCUSSION.

It is known that a freshly prepared colloid attains to its equilibrium state slowly or otherwise, depending on the nature of the system, on simply allowing it to stand. This is the so-called 'ageing'. During this period, there occur reactions (which are almost always irreversible), such as the hydrolysis of the dispersed material and the passage from the latter of the stabilising (or opposite) ions and molecules, into the continuous medium and outside. These affect the size of the particles and some of their characteristic constants such as the charge, the dielectric constant, the state of the micellar hydration, etc. These reactions are accelerated at the higher temperatures used in 'thermoageing'. Presumably, therefore, 'thermoageing' differs from ordinary ageing in degree and not so much in kind. The behaviour of colloidal HgS is interesting; it shows that 'ageing' and coagulation might be to an appreciable extent cognate, in origin and mechanism of reaction. The above colloid *autocoagulates* (that is, coagulates, without the introduction of an external material) simply by 'ageing' in about 10 days, or in a very much shorter period by 'thermoageing'. In this, the release of H₂S (or a similar stabilising material) would appear to be a reasonable factor. The extent to which such a factor would operate depends chiefly upon the nature of the colloid for example, colloid As₂S₃ can stand, *i.e.*, 'age' for long periods of time and 'thermoage' for at least 24 hours without appreciable instabilisation taking place, although the H₂S, which is known to be a stabiliser for the colloid, is expected to be released slowly or rapidly depending on the temperature to which the system is exposed.

It is interesting to note from the results in Table I that η , the viscosity is not altered always in the same sense as a result of 'thermoageing'. In the majority of the cases studied, η decreases slightly on 'thermoageing', in four cases out of nine it has increased. The case of colloidal selenium is peculiar in that 'thermoageing' does not produce any sensible change in η . In this connection it is of interest to recall an earlier finding in these laboratories, *viz.*, that in numerous coagulations of colloid As₂S₃ (Joshi and Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*), and colloid Sb₂S₃ (Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 103) by *mercury chloride*, the viscosity of the coagulating system remained *stationary*. This shows that in so far as 'thermoageing' is analogous to coagulation, viscosity change [and on independent evidence (*loc. cit.*) even turbidity] is no *general* measure of the degree of the corresponding micellar change involved. The marked influence of the nature of the micellar material on η is shown

by the result in Table I, that while 'thermoageing' leads to an increase of η in the case of Al_2O_3 sol, the opposite is observed with the apparently similar Fe_2O_3 . It also follows that although simpler than coagulation, 'ageing' is too complex a phenomenon to be measured by change of any single property. Results are available from the work of numerous investigators on changes by 'ageing' in the adsorptive capacity, flocculation value, micellar change, double refraction, cataphoretic velocity, intensity of the Tyndall cone, conductivity and viscosity. These do not allow of any simple generalisation by reason of mutually exclusive findings, which change from colloid to colloid. The result obtained previously in these laboratories, that in 19 colloids 'thermoageing' produces an increase of refractivity is interesting. In by far the majority of cases and in agreement with our results (for η) viscosity decreases and conductivity increases by 'ageing'; the latter change is due to the release of ions from the particles into the solution phase.

It is interesting to consider the effect of 'thermoageing' on the transparency as shown by Table I. This property seems to have increased in the majority of cases and might be due to a diminution of particle size, which is in agreement with the earlier finding of a general increase in refractivity, also attributed to the same origin. Usually though not invariably (Joshi and Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*; Joshi and Menon, *loc. cit.*, Joshi and Purushottam, *Current Science*, 1936, 4, 870) coagulation decreases transparency; the contrary might, however be conceived if a simple coalescence leads to an increase in the free inter-particle space. It has been emphasised in previous communications (Joshi and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329, 599; 1934, 11, 133, 555, 573, 797; 1936, 13, 309, 311; *J. chim. phys.*, 1935, 32, 455; *Proc. Acad. Sci. U. P.*, 1935, 5, 41.; *J. Bombay Univ.*, 1935, 4, 140; *Fettchem. Umsch.*, 1936, 3, 36; *Kolloid Z.*, 1936, 76, 145) that both viscosity and transparency changes are inadmissible as a general measure of the corresponding degree of coagulation. The data in Table I support this deduction. Like coagulation, 'thermoageing' represents a certain micellar change. Subject to the above limitation, it is anticipated that increase of viscosity might be accompanied by a diminution of transparency, so familiar in coagulation phenomena. The above results for 'thermoageing' show, however, the inadequacy of such a generalisation. Thus for example, in the case of colloidal MnO_2 , 'thermoageing' produces an increase both in viscosity and transparency; in Fe_2O_3 and As_2S_3 sols, both these quantities diminish, the former rather slightly. These results show that either 'ageing' and coagulation are almost entirely different, or what is more probable, viscosity and

transparency do not necessarily increase and diminish respectively in a coagulation.

Work is in progress on the absorption spectra of a number of 'thermoaged' sols. These results will be published shortly.

S U M M A R Y.

The changes of viscosity and transparency (for white light) consequent on 'thermoaging' are studied for two oil emulsions and colloidal solutions of As_2S_3 , Sb_2S_3 , MnO_2 , HgS , Fe_2O_3 and Prussian blue. The last two show change of colour. Majority of others show a decrease in viscosity and increase in transparency. In some cases, decrease in transparency is accompanied by a like change in viscosity, and *vice versa*. It is suggested that these properties, *viz.*, viscosity and opacity do not necessarily increase during coagulation.

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SPIRO-COMPOUNDS. PART IV FORMATION OF SPIRO-COMPOUNDS FROM CYCLOPENTANONE. SYNTHESIS OF CYCLOPENTANE-SPIRO-CYCLOPENTANE AND ITS DERIVATIVES.

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It follows from the model that *cyclopentane* has got a coplaner structure, whereas the *cyclohexane* ring is in a dynamic condition changing from one multiplaner form to another, thus passing through an intermediate stage when it is coplaner and consequently a strained one. Now assuming that the average condition of the vibrating framework is between the uniplaner and strainless conditions, the difference in the case of formation and stability of the analogous spiro-compounds built up with these two types of rings will be a measure of the difference in strain in them. With the hope of gaining some quantitative idea of the nature of strain in these rings, spiro-